

PENGEMBANGAN MEDIA PEMBELAJARAN PENGENALAN SISTEM OPERASI BERBASIS ANDROID

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk mengembangkan media pembelajaran berbasis Android dengan tahapan *analysis, design, development, implementation, dan evaluation*. Subjek penelitian yaitu mahasiswa semester IV Pendidikan TIK IKIP PGRI Pontianak. Metode penelitian menggunakan *research and development* dengan pendekatan ADDIE. Instrumen penelitian menggunakan angket. Teknik analisis data menggunakan deskriptif kuantitatif. Hasil penelitian yaitu: (1) Media pembelajaran yang dikembangkan dapat diterapkan berdasarkan hasil pada tahapan *analysis*; (2) Media pembelajaran berhasil dirancang pada tahapan *design*; (3) Media pembelajaran yang telah divalidasi dilakukan perbaikan sesuai saran dari validator pada tahapan *development*; (4) Media pembelajaran berhasil diterapkan ke subjek penelitian pada tahapan *implementation*; dan (5) Subjek penelitian menyatakan “Setuju” dan “Lebih Efektif” penggunaan media pembelajaran yang dikembangkan dalam proses pembelajaran.

Kata Kunci: pengembangan, media pembelajaran, Android.

Abstract

The research objective was to develop an Android-based learning media with stages of analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. The subjects of the research were the fourth-semester students of ICT Education at IKIP PGRI Pontianak. The research method used research and development with the ADDIE approach. The research instrument used a questionnaire. Data analysis techniques using descriptive-quantitative. The results of the research: (1) The developed learning media can be applied based on the results at the analysis stage; (2) Learning media successfully designed at the design stage; (3) The validated learning media is improved according to the suggestions from the validators at the development stage; (4) Learning media successfully applied to respondents at the implementation stage; and (5) Respondents stated "Agree" and "More Effective" in the use of instructional media developed in the learning process.

Keywords: development, learning media, Android.